

**Proximal Migration of a Double-Pigtail Biliary Stent into the Gallbladder:
A Rare Intraoperative Surprise during Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy**

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Abstract

Introduction: Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) with stent placement is the standard of care for managing choledocholithiasis. While stent migration is a known complication, proximal migration into the gallbladder is exceptionally rare.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 74-year-old male with a history of COVID-19 pneumonia who presented with obstructive jaundice. He underwent ERCP performed by the medical gastroenterology department, where a 10 Fr, 10 cm double-pigtail plastic stent was placed following sphincteroplasty. Three weeks later, the patient was referred to our surgical unit for an elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Intraoperatively, the stent was unexpectedly discovered entirely within the gallbladder lumen. The stent was retrieved, and the cholecystectomy was completed successfully.

Discussion: Proximal stent migration is associated with benign biliary disease and larger bile duct diameters. This case is unique as migration occurred despite the use of a double-pigtail stent, which is designed to prevent such displacement. This highlights the diagnostic challenge of "silent" migration and emphasizes the necessity for surgeons to maintain a high index of suspicion in post-ERCP patients.

Conclusion: Although rare, biliary stents can migrate into the gallbladder even when anti-migration designs are used. Surgical teams must be prepared for this anomaly to avoid intraoperative complications.

Keywords: Biliary stent migration, Gallbladder, ERCP, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy.

Introduction

Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) is a widely utilized and effective procedure for the treatment of benign and malignant biliary obstructions [1]. While generally safe, complications such as pancreatitis, bleeding, and cholangitis are well-documented. Biliary stent migration is an uncommon late complication, occurring in approximately 3.5% to 10% of cases [2, 3].

Migration typically occurs distally into the duodenum; however, proximal migration into the biliary tree can also occur. Migration specifically into the gallbladder is an exceptionally rare phenomenon that poses unique diagnostic and surgical challenges.

We report a case of a 74-year-old male who underwent ERCP for choledocholithiasis. Three weeks later, during a laparoscopic cholecystectomy, we unexpectedly discovered the biliary stent entirely within the gallbladder lumen.

Case Presentation

A 74-year-old male presented to the internal medicine department with signs of obstructive jaundice and acute cholangitis. His medical history was significant for recent severe pneumonia secondary to COVID-19.

The patient underwent ERCP performed by the medical gastroenterology team. The endoscopic view identified a small ampulla located between two large diverticula. The cholangiogram revealed a dilated common bile duct (CBD) and hepatic ducts with multiple large filling defects (Figure 1). Following a partial sphincterotomy and sphincteroplasty dilated up to 12 mm, approximately 10 large stones were swept from the duct. then a 10 Fr, 10 cm double-pigtail plastic stent inserted into the CBD. The procedure was noted as successful with no immediate complications.

Three weeks post-ERCP, the patient was referred to our surgical department for an elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Intraoperatively, extensive adhesions were found, likely secondary to the recent cholangitis. During the dissection of the gallbladder, a firm tubular structure was felt within the gallbladder that made the gallbladder opened in its fundus and the biliary stent was found coiled entirely within the lumen (Figure 2). No portion of the stent remained in the cystic duct or CBD. The stent was retrieved, and the cholecystectomy was completed. The patient had an uneventful postoperative course and was discharged on postoperative day one.

Figure 1: Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangiopancreatography (ERCP)

Figure 2: Intraoperative photograph showing the retrieved 10 Fr double-pigtail biliary stent which was found located entirely within the gallbladder lumen

Figure 3: Gallbladder specimen the stent

Discussion

The migration of a biliary stent into the gallbladder is a rare clinical event that creates a diagnostic blind spot for the surgical team. Arhan et al. noted that while migration is more frequent in benign strictures, proximal migration usually involves the hepatic ducts rather than the cystic duct [1]. Consequently, literature on migration into the gallbladder is sparse, with only a few cases reported globally, such as those by Yagnik et al. [4] and Bhoil et al. [5].

Mechanisms and Risk Factors

The mechanism of migration in this case is particularly noteworthy due to the type of stent used. According to Kawaguchi et al., straight-type stents are significantly more prone to migration than pigtail stents, as the coiled ends of pigtail stents are designed to anchor them within the duct [2]. In our case, however, a double-pigtail stent was used, yet proximal migration still occurred.

This suggests that other risk factors overcame the mechanical design of the stent. Kawaguchi et al. identified that a bile duct diameter >10 mm and benign disease are major risk factors for proximal migration [2]. In malignant strictures, tumor overgrowth often anchors the stent, whereas in benign conditions like choledocholithiasis, the stent floats freely. In our patient, the ERCP report noted a dilated biliary system requiring sphincteroplasty up to 12 mm. We hypothesize that the combination of a widely dilated CBD and a patent, dilated cystic duct allowed the proximal pigtail to rotate and insinuate itself into the gallbladder, eventually pulling the entire stent inside due to bowel or ductal motility.

Diagnostic and Surgical Implications

This case highlights a critical need for communication between the medical gastroenterology team and the surgical team. Bhoil et al. discussed the possibility of "misplacement vs. migration," suggesting that in some cases, the stent might be inadvertently deployed into the cystic duct during ERCP [5]. However, in our case, the patient was asymptomatic for three weeks post-ERCP, suggesting the stent was initially placed correctly in the common bile duct and migrated silently.

Our intraoperative finding shares similarities with the case reported by Yagnik et al., where a stent was also found during cholecystectomy [4]. However, in their case, the stent was partially lodged in the cystic duct and was inadvertently transected. In our patient, the stent was entirely within the gallbladder lumen. This distinction is vital for the operating surgeon: a stent hidden entirely in the gallbladder may not be palpable at Calot's triangle, whereas one protruding into the cystic duct poses a significant risk of iatrogenic injury to the common bile duct if not recognized before clipping.

Conclusion

Proximal migration of a biliary stent into the gallbladder is a rare but possible complication of ERCP. Surgeons performing interval cholecystectomy post-ERCP should maintain a high index of suspicion, even when "anti-migration" pigtail stents are used, particularly in patients with benign disease and dilated ducts. If extensive inflammation or adhesions are present, careful dissection is paramount to avoid injury to migrated hardware.

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